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Reframing Political Islam as Authoritarian Statecraft

In the post-colonial Muslim world, political elites faced a central dilemma: how to integrate Islam into modern statehood after centuries of shared religious authority had been fractured by colonialism, empire collapse, and external domination. Historically, Islamic governance was defined not by theocratic absolutism but by a contested balance between political power and religious legitimacy. From the Umayyads and Abbasids to the Ottomans, Islamic states operated through a structure of shared sovereignty. Rulers upheld public order while the ‘Ulama’ served as legal and moral authorities. But the abolition of the caliphate in 1924, followed by European imperialism and the rise of authoritarian regimes, shattered this arrangement and left modern states to redefine religion’s political function under radically new conditions. What emerged were strategic, state-driven reinventions of Islam, not expressions of divine mandate, but instruments of nationalist legitimacy, ideological warfare, and regime survival. While historians have examined the rise of political Islam and the violent extremism that followed, few studies analyze how these regimes deliberately reshaped Islam’s public image or explore the reasoning behind these state-driven narratives. Current scholarship often treats Orientalist depictions and colonial reforms as background context rather than as active political strategies. While this points out how states turned to Islam under pressure, it has also contributed to a conflation of political Islam with Islamism, obscuring how regimes have used religion differently depending on historical context, internal threat, or international pressure. What these narratives overlook is the political flexibility of Islam under authoritarian rule, and how in certain cases, it has been reengineered not for mass mobilization or revolutionary urgency, but for technocratic regulation and managed legitimacy. This paper positions the United Arab Emirates as representing the possibility of a third wave of political Islam: a post-ideological form rooted in administrative management rather than doctrinal authority. By tracing the evolution from Egypt’s statist Islam to Saudi Arabia’s ideological Islam and now the UAE’s calibrated Islam, this paper reframes political Islam not as an inherent threat or militant movement, but as a flexible instrument of

authoritarian statecraft, reengineered to meet the evolving demands of governance, security, and legitimacy in the modern era.

Across the contemporary Middle East, states have consistently reshaped the political role of Islam in response to evolving pressures: from colonial legacies and Cold War alignments to internal unrest and global security threats. The disintegration of the Ottoman Caliphate in 1924 left a religious vacuum across the Sunni world, stripping Islamic institutions of transnational legitimacy and forcing newly independent regimes to reconstruct the link between sovereignty and spiritual authority. These efforts were shaped not only by institutional collapse but by the enduring imprint of European imperialism, which disrupted traditional centers of Islamic jurisprudence, suppressed pan-Arab and Islamist movements, and introduced Western legal and educational models into the heart of Muslim societies. In Egypt, this resulted in the nationalization of Al-Azhar and the violent repression of the Muslim Brotherhood under Gamal Abdel Nasser, as Islam was subordinated to a secular, developmentalist nationalism. In Saudi Arabia, by contrast, its Cold War alliance with the United States turned Wahhabi clerics into global ideologues, where oil wealth funded transnational da'wa efforts, mosque and madrasa networks, and religious NGOs aimed at combating secular ideologies and Soviet influence, and bolstering the Kingdom's Islamic authority. Both models responded to the crisis of postcolonial legitimacy, but each reflected a different method of control: Egypt turned inward to centralize religious discourse; Saudi Arabia looked outward to export its interpretation of Islam. In the wake of 9/11 and the Arab Spring, the Emirati state institutionalized a tightly controlled form of Islam through regulatory councils, state-managed sermons, and a rhetoric of moderation designed to insulate the regime from both domestic radicalism and international scrutiny. These three cases reveal not just variations in how Islam is used, but a deeper continuity: the transformation of religion from a source of moral authority into a tool of modern governance, tailored to fit the ideological, geopolitical, and technological demands of the authoritarian state.

In postcolonial Egypt, Islam's militant public portrayal did not merge from theology, but from the political needs of a state seeking unity, legitimacy, and postcolonial sovereignty, which required a carefully weaponized religious rhetoric. Following Britain's withdrawal and the fragmentation of pan-Arab and Islamic authority, Gamal Abdel Nasser constructed a nationalist regime that sought to project strength while consolidating control over every source of moral legitimacy. Religion became a key tool in this project. When Nasser announced the nationalization of the Suez Canal in 1956, he staged the event not as administrative policy but as a redemptive act of historical justice. Speaking before a massive crowd in Alexandria, he invoked Egypt's colonial humiliation alongside the language of martyrdom and sacrifice: "120,000 of our sons lost their lives" digging the canal, and now the nation would rise "by our sweat, our tears, the souls of our martyrs and the skulls of those who died in 1856," to frame his nationalist project as sacred and morally righteous tailored to a majority Islamic audience. The Suez Canal became not just a reclaimed asset, but a sacred symbol. In a moment of high drama, he declared, "We shall all fight to the last drop of our blood... for the sake of Egypt," a statement that did not simply summon patriotism but infused national sovereignty with the moral charge of jihad. Additionally, his rebuke of Western critics stating "Whenever I hear talk from Washington, I shall say: 'Die of your fury!'" fused anticolonial defiance with righteous zeal, casting Egypt as a moral force in a fallen world¹. This points out the lingering effects of colonial rule and its impact in fueling authoritarian sentiment and dictating the country's next moves. This discrete religious language was not part of an Islamic political vision. It was tactical. Just five years later, the 1961 Al-Azhar Law brought Egypt's top Islamic institution under presidential control, expanded its curriculum to secular subjects, and placed imams on the state payroll. Though he championed secular nationalism, Nasser had no intention of surrendering moral authority to religious scholars. Instead, he invoked Islam when it served his image and suppressed it when it challenged his monopoly. His speeches suggested divine conviction yet his policies revealed political calculation. In the end, Nasser's regime did not secularize Islam, it nationalized it, developing sacred

¹ Nasser, Gamal Abdel. 1956. "Speech by President Nasser, Alexandria, July 26 [1956] (Extract) | Wilson Center Digital Archive." [Digitalarchive.wilsoncenter.org](https://digitalarchive.wilsoncenter.org). July 26, 1956. <https://digitalarchive.wilsoncenter.org/document/speech-president-nasser-alexandria-july-26-1956-extract>.

language not to implement sharia, but to eliminate dissent. As later developments would show, any vision of Islam that stood outside the state, however peaceful or moral, would be branded extremist and brought under control.

This regime-led weaponization of Islam relied not only on politicizing religious language, but on silencing alternative Islamic visions like the Muslim Brotherhood backed by Islamist thinkers like Sayyid Qutb, that could coexist with the state's monopoly on power. In his book *Milestones*, Qutb framed Islam not as a tool of the nation, but as a divine project rooted in freedom from human subjugation. "The Jihad of Islam," he wrote, "is to secure complete freedom for every man... releasing him from servitude to other human beings so that he may serve God." This was not encouraging violence, it was a rejection of nationalist ideologies that demanded obedience to rulers in place and in the name of God. Essentially, Qutb rejected the idea that jihad should be reduced to self-defense, arguing: "Those who say that Islamic Jihad was merely for the defence of the 'homeland of Islam' diminish the greatness of the Islamic way of life... This is not the Islamic point of view... it is completely alien to Islamic consciousness." Here, Qutb directly challenged the state's narrative, which had framed militarism as a necessary expression of national sovereignty. His concept of jihad, along with many other thinkers behind the Muslim Brotherhood who were silenced, was not about aggression but about dismantling "those oppressive political systems under which people are prevented from expressing their freedom to choose whatever beliefs they want."² Yet this emancipatory vision threatened the regime's political project. In a fragile postcolonial moment, when Egypt was emerging from British domination and striving to project a unified, modern image, an autonomous Islamic discourse posed a serious liability. Qutb's moral vision did not reject statehood, but it rejected sacralized state power. It was the independence they brought of a divinely grounded islam, independent of state authority which undermined national unity that had to be suppressed. So the regime rebranded his ideas as radicalism, grouping them with the few publicized extremist thinkers, casting the entire Brotherhood as enemies of the nation rather than critics of

² Qutb, Sayyid. *Milestones (Ma'alim fi'l-Tariq)*. Translated by A. B. al-Mehri. Birmingham: Maktabah Booksellers and Publishers, 2006.

authoritarianism. The Islam they portrayed had to be seen as militant, not because Qutb made it so, but because the regime needed it to be so it could justify its own militarization to maintain power. That non-militant, reformist Islam would not disappear entirely, but it would have to wait for a political environment more stable and secure than Egypt's authoritarian revolution could provide.

Where Egypt suppressed rival Islamic visions to consolidate authoritarian control, Saudi Arabia mobilized Wahhabism as a tool of regime protection, weaponizing it not just to enforce domestic unity, but to counter Nasserite and communist threats and assert international legitimacy amid Cold War polarization. Religion, particularly Wahhabism, often portrayed as militant, became an instrument of national cohesion and international legitimacy. In a 1966 meeting with President Lyndon B. Johnson, King Faisal linked Saudi domestic reform to the broader global threat of communism, describing education and development as instead of theological imperatives, being impediments against political infiltration. He warned of "subjects...which would fashion the tender young minds of our youth in a way prejudicial to the interests of our country," referring to secular ideas imported from Egyptian instructors. "We have come to the decision," he said, "that it would be unwise to our future generations to place these easily molded minds in the hands of strangers who do not share with us the genuine interests of our country." Faisal's anxiety was not simply about curriculum, it was about control. As Johnson affirmed, the two shared "the same views as to the Communist dangers to the area and the tactics the Soviets resort to." Faced with the appeal of socialist nationalism abroad and the logistical constraints of state building at home, the monarchy positioned Wahhabi Islam as a tool of ideological insulation, presenting an antidote to atheistic communism and a badge of cultural authenticity. Saudi Arabia needed a theology that could convey moral clarity, project order, and consolidate loyalty, especially in contrast to Nasser's Arab socialism, which was gaining ground as a revolutionary model. To secure international legitimacy, King Faisal emphasized the Kingdom's role in resisting radical ideologies: "We deeply appreciate the sacrifices and the efforts expended by the U.S. in behalf of humanity," he told Johnson, affirming his alignment

with the West's anti-Communist bloc, and partnership opportunity between this newly found alliance³. In this framework, Islam was not only nationalized, but internationalized, cast as both an internal disciplinary force and a diplomatic credential. The political strategy was based around the idea extreme religiosity could counter extreme secularism, especially when both were useful in fortifying the state and securing its alliances.

Once a tool of political survival, the Kingdom's use of militant religious discourse is now openly framed by its own leadership as a distortion, one that must be undone not by reinventing Islam, but by returning to its non politicized core. In his 2022 Atlantic interview, Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman directly confronts the legacy of extremism, clarifying that the problem was never Islam itself, but its manipulation: "We are going back to the real teachings of Islam, the way that the Prophet and the four Rightly Guided caliphs lived, which was open and peaceful societies." What he rejects is not faith, but its weaponization: "The extremists hijacked and changed our religion into something new for their own interests." This retrospective reframing marks a decisive shift. Where once Wahhabi discourse was deployed to bolster regime loyalty and counter ideological threats, it is now acknowledged as having produced "a mix of many things... that led to the creation of the most extreme terrorist groups." This reiterates my earlier point about Egypt as he clarifies "It's not all the Muslim Brotherhood," claiming a small subset was elevated and publicized in ways that justified a sweeping campaign against the group. The violence of a few was used to represent the totality. Even the legacy of Muhammad Ibn 'Abd al-Wahhab is relativized: "He is not a prophet... just a scholar like many other scholars... His writing has been used by many extremists for their own agendas." The Crown Prince further explains that "his students were the only people who knew how to read and write," so history was "written from their perspective", demonstrating how early Wahhabi dominance in religious production was not a reflection of Islamic truth, but of unequal access to literacy and power. Such statements do not signal a theological

³ Johnson, Lyndon B. *Memorandum of Conversation with King Faisal*. June 21, 1966. In *Foreign Relations of the United States, 1964–1968, Volume XXI: Near East Region; Arabian Peninsula*, edited by Harriet D. Schwar and David S. Patterson. Washington: U.S. Government Printing Office, 2000. Document 275. Johnson Library, National Security File, Country File, Saudi Arabia, Memos, Vol. I, 12/63–4/67.

awakening, they mark a political rebranding, one that affirms the state's authority to define, reinterpret, and regulate Islamic legitimacy. As the Crown Prince puts it, "In Islamic law, the head of the Islamic establishment is wali al-amr, the ruler... the final fatwa is for the King," reminding the audience how religious authority in the Kingdom has long been subordinated to political power⁴. The message is clear: just as the regime once shaped Islam to sustain its militarized posture, it now reshapes it to sustain modernization. This is not reform from below, it is top-down recalibration. But its rationale mirrors that of an earlier era: political necessity. What changes is the goal. Where Wahhabism once projected discipline and defiance, today's Islam must project openness, pragmatism, and peace. The theology remains grounded in state power, but the vision has shifted. The same mechanism once used to sacralize military is now used to sanction reform, and in doing so, reveals the problem was never Islam's doctrine, but the state's designs upon it.

Extending the present Saudi approach into a new era, the United Arab Emirates showcases a recalibrated vision of Islam, one that emerges not from crisis or ideological insecurity, but from a secure, postcolonial, and globally integrated political landscape. In this context, religion is not deployed to rescue the state but to rebrand it. Nowhere is this clearer than in the public staging of the UAE's interfaith diplomacy, especially during the 2019 Interreligious Meeting in Abu Dhabi, where Pope Francis praised the country for having "transformed the desert into a prosperous and hospitable place," calling it a "meeting place between cultures and religions." Framing the UAE as crossroads of civilization rather than a site of religious repression, the speech cast the nation's Islamic identity as inherently cooperative, peaceful, and future-oriented. Francis declared: "It is comforting to note how in this country investments are being made not only in the extraction of the earth's resources, but also in those of the heart, in the education of young people." The UAE, while still an authoritarian state, has cultivated an image of security that contrasts sharply with the coercive religious governance portrayed in most scholarship on political Islam. As the Pope observed, the country's "respect and tolerance" allow believers to "preserve

⁴ Saudi Gazette. 2022. "Full Transcript of Crown Prince Interview on Reforms, Religion, Future of Saudi Arabia and Relations with US." Saudigazette. March 3, 2022. <https://saudigazette.com.sa/article/617738>.

not only the image of the great works erected in the desert, but also the image of a nation that includes and embraces all,” a vision that reframes Islamic governance as not only compatible with pluralism, but actively generative of it⁵.

This rhetorical performance is not confined to the global stage, it is mirrored by concrete domestic strategies that shape how Islam is practiced and internalized within Emirati society. In addition to establishing the UAE fatwa council and state-managed khutbahs, the regime launched a national Fatwa app, which offers ruling and religious guidance designed to promote a culture of “moderation, mercy, and social cohesion.” Rather than focusing on prohibition or theological rigidity, the app encourages users to embrace “ease,” “kindness,” and “unity of the ummah” not as mobilizing slogans this time, but as social values. Similarly, the Council for Fatwa’s 2024 zakat and sacrifice manual opens not with legalism but with “the values of compassion, kindness, and ihsān,” situating piety in terms of service and accessibility, not fear or discipline⁶. Here, Islam is not instrumentalized for ideological warfare, but calibrated for reputation-building and domestic management.

This model departs sharply from prior iterations in Egypt and Saudi Arabia, showcasing the complex dynamics behind political Islam. While those states weaponized Islam to defend sovereignty or project regional authority, the UAE’s post-ideological Islam is technocratic, pacifying, and diplomatically performative. What makes this version distinct is that it does not require religious militancy to assert strength, nor moral absolutism to assert purity. It functions instead as a carefully managed soft power tool, where religious legitimacy is curated to stabilize society, project tolerance, and signal alignment with global norms. It contradicts much of the historical literature that treats political Islam as necessarily militant or mass-oriented. In the UAE, Islam is neither revolutionary nor reactive, it is administrative, intentional, and deeply strategically contained. Unlike earlier regimes that used Islam to survive political

⁵ Libreria Editrice Vaticana. 2019. “Apostolic Journey to the United Arab Emirates: Interreligious Meeting at the Founder’s Memorial (Abu Dhabi, 4 February 2019) | Francis.” Vatican.va. February 4, 2019. https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/speeches/2019/february/documents/papa-francesco_20190204_emiratia-rabi-incontrointerreligioso.html.

⁶ The UAE Council for Fatwa. 2025. “Fatwas and Rulings on Zakat, Sacrifice and Aqeeqah.” Fatwauae.gov.ae. 2025. <https://fatwauae.gov.ae/en/publications/Fatwas-and-rulings-on-zakat-sacrifice-and-aqeeqah>.

volatility, the UAE's state-led Islam is engineered to thrive in a time of security, projecting moderation not because it is newly discovered, but because the state is finally strong enough to afford it.

The story of political Islam cannot be understood apart from the trauma of colonial subjugation and the distortions it produced. As thinkers like Arslan and Ostrorog observed in the early 20th century, European power occupied Muslim lands and undermined Islamic political legitimacy itself. Through both scholarship and policy, Muslims were portrayed as too irrational, stagnant, or primitive to govern modern states. This was a tool of imperial control that continues to shape global perceptions of Islam today. In the wake of empire's collapse, postcolonial states were left to assert authority within a global system designed to deny them that very possibility. Viewing the Muslim Brotherhood and Nasser's ruling as a more complete, less stoic, battle of regimes trying to survive and revive its people, opens up this interpretation. What followed was not organic religious revival, but strategic recalibration: Islam was transformed into a political instrument, reengineered to fight back and assert sovereignty, suppress dissent, and manage international scrutiny. The authoritarian turn in many Muslim countries did not reflect any intrinsic incompatibility between Islam and democracy, it reflected the fragile conditions of postcolonial statehood, defined by legacy, instability, and the ongoing need to perform legitimacy.

This legacy also produced a conflation that remains deeply consequential: the assumption that Islam itself is responsible for the policies of the states that invoke it. As this paper has shown, that assumption collapses theological tradition into regime tactics and treats political Islam as a singular phenomenon rather than a set of contingent responses to vastly different pressures. Egypt mobilized Islam to sacralize postcolonial nationalism; Saudi Arabia used it to build ideological alignment with the West and contain communism; the UAE, decades later, has constructed a technocratic Islam suited to a globalized, image-conscious world. These variations are not theological, they are strategic. Yet the dominant lens still treats Islam as the driver rather than the vehicle. Even the structure of modern interviews with state leaders, like the one with Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman, reinforces this pattern as the interviewer jumps from extremism directly to Wahhabism, unconsciously reenacting the same conflation that has plagued discourse around Islam, reducing political complexity into religious

blame. What makes this account especially valuable is that it shows the internal undoing of that narrative. The regime now articulates, on its own terms, how its past policies distorted Islam to reassert control over its image. Modern sources like this are critical as their inclusion in scholarship helps challenge inherited stereotypes, complicate Islamophobic framings, and push back against the rhetoric used to justify ongoing violence and surveillance against Muslim societies.

The UAE's model offers a revealing case of political Islam shaped not by crisis, but by stability and global integration. Unlike postcolonial Egypt or Cold War Saudi Arabia, its political needs demand not mass mobilization but internal order and international legitimacy. This has enabled the state to craft a technocratic, pacified, and diplomatically performative Islam, prioritizing moderation, discipline, and reputational clarity. Still authoritarian, the regime does not use Islam defensively, instead as a governance and image-building tool. Importantly, its global narrative now aligns better with domestic practice with centralized sermons, fatwa councils digitalized, and rulings emphasize compassion, mercy and unity. These are not signs of religious withdrawal, they are of calibrated containment rendering Islam legible as a source of cohesion rather than threat. The UAE challenges the Western binary between secularism and extremism, showing that an Islamic state can be neither liberal nor militant, but stable, strategic, and forward-looking.

To understand political Islam today, we must reorient our questions. Instead of asking whether religion and politics are compatible, we should be asking what kinds of states are producing which forms of Islam, and why. The UAE does not offer a universal model, nor does it escape critique, but it does force a reassessment of how political Islam is defined, studied, and engaged. It reminds us that Islam has always been shaped by the politics of its moment, and that today's regimes aren't pure theological actors, but modern governments operating within the aftershocks of empire, war, and global inequality. The future of political Islam will depend not on reclaiming some imagined purity, but on recognizing how belief, governance, and legitimacy have been woven together, and how that weaving can take forms far more nuanced than the tropes allow. In this light, political Islam is not a relic of the past, nor a threat to the future. It is a dynamic tool of statecraft that when studied honestly may help us rethink what modern

governance could look like when built on dignity, inclusion, and strategic imagination, when given the opportunity to independently flourish.

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